

D4.2 Möbius open call: Fantasy

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Executive summary

The following document illustrates the steps taken to launch of Möbius call for manuscripts on 08/11/2021. The goal is to clarify all the passages that led to the creation of the Terms and conditions and the application form.

Table of Contents

REVISION HISTORY	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	3
TERMINOLOGY AND ACRONYMS.....	3
1. INTRODUCTION.....	4
2. MÖBIUS OPEN CALL FOR MANUSCRIPTS.....	4
2.1 THEMATIC ORIENTATION	4
2.2 ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA	4
2.3 PRIZE	5
2.4 IP RIGHTS	5
2.5 EVALUATION CRITERIA AND WORKFLOW	5
2.6 PRIVACY AND POPD ISSUES.....	6
3. DISSEMINATION CAMPAIGN	7
4. TERMS AND CONDITIONS	8
4.1 TERMS AND CONDITIONS.....	8
ELIGIBILITY CONDITIONS	9
PRIZE.....	9
EVALUATION CRITERIA AND COMMUNICATION OF RESULTS.....	9
IP RIGHTS	10
DATA PROTECTION.....	10
5. WEB SUBMISSION FORM (TYPEFORM).....	12
6. CONCLUSIONS.....	18

Terminology and Acronyms

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>PMB</i>	<i>Project Management Board</i>
<i>PMP</i>	<i>Project Management Plan</i>
<i>STAB</i>	<i>Scientific and Technical Advisory Board</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Introduction

The call for manuscripts is part of Work Package 4 (lead by Eurecat), objectives of which are:

- To select and design the pre-production scripts for the Möbius experimental productions.
- To develop a prototype for the Möbius book following a participatory methodology in which improved upon in different release cycles according to agile principles and evaluated using different beta-testers groups.

Bookabook as leader of the task 4.2 Möbius Book pre-production task. It is responsible for carrying out all necessary pre-production activities for selecting and preparing the contents that will become part of the Möbius Book Experience. Work in this task will be organized in two phases:

1. Preparation of the Open call (until M9)
2. Manuscript evaluation

This deliverable briefly describes the decision-making process behind the call for manuscripts. In particular, the design and development of the Terms and Conditions (See Section 4), and the dissemination strategy to maximize subscription (in cooperation with T3.2 and T6.1).

2. Möbius Open Call for manuscripts

The Möbius project is set to launch a call for manuscripts in M9. The goal of this call is to collect prosumer's works upon which create at least one experimental production. The call needed to be carefully tailored to comply with Möbius contractual framework. Bookabook and EUT lead the process for creating the terms and conditions, and the application forms.

2.1 Thematic orientation

In GA the theme is open. The call was generically called “Fantasy”, as it is one of the most popular genres among amateur writers.

During the preliminary discussion about the terms and conditions, it was agreed that the call would connect with the **New European Bauhaus** initiative. This connection would be realised by setting a thematic orientation within the Fantasy genre and asking authors “to imagine and build a beautiful and liveable future” with their stories.

2.2 Eligibility criteria

As for eligibility criteria, it was decided to include the following:

- **Ownership:** Original, unpublished work, so that authors are the sole owners of the manuscripts.
- **Length:** Manuscripts should have a maximum length of **6.000 characters**, including spaces. This limitation was set to receive complete stories that could be transformed into a 6-minute audiobook production.

- **Languages:** EUT and Bookabook as leaders of WP4 and T4.2, respectively, and chairs of the evaluation committee, suggested to accept manuscripts in English, Italian and Spanish. In both organizations there are personnel involved in the project with proficiency in all three languages and thus able to evaluate the manuscripts. A motivation behind this decision is the opportunity to maximize subscription in other languages than English.
- **Authors:** Author(s) must be natural persons, over 18 years old, and citizens and/or residents of **EU-27 countries**¹, plus associated countries or in process of becoming associated to **Horizon Europe**².
- **Number of manuscripts:** Each author may submit a **maximum of two manuscripts**.
- **Time and form:** To be eligible, all authors must apply through the **Möbius website** within the application period (from November 8th, 2021- to January 15th, 2022).

2.3 Prize

Möbius call will have two prizes: 1st place: 1,500 euro, and 2nd and 3rd place: 500 euro each.

The prizes will be handed out *in kind*. This is, via a gift card or redeemable coupon by an online or physical store in their location. This choice of prize was necessary to comply with H2020 rules. The Möbius project does not foresees budget Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP), therefore any cash handouts would not be possible.

The Möbius consortium may declare the prizes desert in case no manuscript has necessary quality. In that case, the consortium will restore to other suitable samples.

2.4 IP rights

Partners Bookabook and FEP provided a first draft of IP rights cession for the Möbius call for manuscripts. The drafts regarding the acquisition of the commercial rights were initially selected from Bookabook existing contracts. However, there was a discussion on the suitability of a commercial agreement in exchange for the prize amounts. Partner KUL contributed to the discussion from their IP and copyright expertise. This resulted in the current wording by which non-exclusive and non-commercial rights are acquired by EUT (as project coordinator) for the limited purpose of realising the experimental productions of the Möbius project in exchange for the prizes.

2.5 Evaluation criteria and workflow

The manuscripts will be evaluated against the following criteria.

¹ EU-27: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden.

² Associated countries: Iceland, Norway. In negotiation (as of 4/10/2021): Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Israel, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, Morocco, North Macedonia, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_horizon-atom_en.pdf

- Excellence and originality of the manuscript.
- Alignment to the theme: the future we dream about.
- Its potential for creating a compelling multimedia experience (e.g., through rich sceneries, soundscapes, dialogues, etc.)

The Evaluation committee will be formed by partners Bookabook and Eurecat. The evaluation workflow will be as follows:

- Bookabook receives manuscripts directly from the application form in the [website](#). They evaluate the submissions and rank them for their literary quality and originality following their standard procedures.
- Preselected manuscripts will be then evaluated and ranked by EUT audio production team; they will look for its suitability to create multimedia content/experience.
- Bookabook and EUT meets for the final ranking. The manuscript ranked first after these processes will be the winning one.
- In case of a tie, the manuscripts will be shared with the consortium and proceed to voting.

Winning authors will be notified before **March 15, 2022**. Results will be published on the website before **April 15, 2022**

2.6 Privacy and POPD issues

The manuscript submission was designed to be compliant to POPD and privacy regulations. Although the submission form is hosted on the website, and the web-hosting partner is FMWC, the partner that receives the manuscript is Bookabook. Therefore, Bookabook is the data collector. The data will be stored until all the data reporting of the project comes to an end. All actions regarding privacy and data collection will be in observance of the GDPR.

Bookabook IT specialists studied a number of tools to collect the submissions. The tool chosen was Typeform because it is an intuitive yet complete platform, which also provides the necessary codes to embed the submission form into the Möbius website.

The submitted information is downloadable in both CSV and XLSX formats, so the next phase (evaluation of the manuscripts) will be easily manageable. A front image which contained Möbius colours was chosen to maintain graphic coherence with the whole project.

On the other hand, it was discussed what data could and should be collected through the forms. It was at last decided that the minimum data information needed to properly run the call were:

Personal or sensitive information	Purpose
Name and last name, e-mail	Contact information for reaching back
Age, Date of Birth, Nationality, Place of residence (country and city)	Eligibility criteria
Gender	Statistical purposes (gender dimension)

3. Dissemination campaign

Partner FMWC as dissemination leader prepared a Communication Toolkit for accompanying the call for manuscripts. This includes suggested copies for LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram. Also, it includes flyers and banners.

A targeted advertising campaign for the Italian, Spanish, EU-27 and H2020 markets is planned to acquire as many manuscripts as possible.

Several other actions, including a possible webinar and translation of the terms and conditions to Italian and Spanish languages are being discussed.

The results of these activities will be reported in the periodic report M18.

Suggested copies

LinkedIn

● MÖBIUS OPEN CALL IS LAUNCHED!

This is a call to all writers, whether you are professional or amateur 🤗
Apply to our #CallForManuscripts and participate in the creation of the first #MobiusBook 📖 a cross-media experience involving 3D audio, original artwork and a virtual reality production!

We are calling for **short original fantasy stories**. We want authors to **imagine and build a livable future**, the future we dream about. In words of Dennis Gabor, Nobel Prize 1971: **"THE FUTURE CANNOT BE PREDICTED, BUT FUTURES CAN BE INVENTED."**

Here you have the eligibility conditions:

- 📄 Unpublished work
- 📄 Max. length of 6.000 characters (including spaces)
- 2️⃣ Max. two submission per author
- 🌍 Participants must be of legal age (>18) and citizens and/or residents of EU-27 countries, plus associated countries or in process of becoming associated to Horizon Europe.
- 🗣️ Languages: English, Italian and Spanish
- 🏆 1,500€ will be awarded for the best story
- 🏆 500€ will be awarded for each of the 2nd and 3rd place.
- 📦 The prizes will be delivered *in kind*

📅 Launch: November 8th, 2021

📅 Deadline: January 15th, 2022

Find out more here 📄

Open Call Flyer

4. Terms and Conditions

Hereinafter, the final Terms and conditions as agreed by all partners and published in Möbius website.

4.1 Terms and conditions

Möbius is an initiative funded under the European Commission Horizon 2020 programme that aims to **reinvigorate the European book publishing industry by remodelling the traditional value chains and business models** uncovering the prosumers potential and delivering new enriched media experiences.

Möbius is eager to **contribute to the New European Bauhaus** and its critical mission of designing “future ways of living, situated at the crossroads between art, culture, social inclusion, science and technology.”

We are calling for **short original fantasy stories conveying this spirit**. We want authors to **imagine and build a liveable future**, the future we dream about. In words of Dennis Gabor, Nobel Prize 1971:

“THE FUTURE CANNOT BE PREDICTED, BUT FUTURES CAN BE INVENTED.”

The winning manuscript will become the first Möbius Book, a cross-media experience involving a 3D audio and virtual reality production, and art installation. The Möbius Book will be showcased in several locations in Europe during 2023 and 2024, as part of the dissemination and demonstrations events of the project. The Möbius Book will remain publicly available in the project’s website for at least a 5-year period after the project finalisation in February 2024.

The call will remain open for submission between **November 8th, 2021 and January 15th, 2022.**

Eligibility conditions

We expect **original, and unpublished works** in any mean (paper, blogs, electronic publications, etc.). We expect stories and characters to be original, containing no intellectual properties of other authors and/or third parties.

Manuscripts should have a maximum length of **6.000 characters**, including spaces.

Author(s) must be natural persons, over 18 years old, and citizens and/or residents of **EU-27 countries**³, plus associated countries or in process of becoming associated to **Horizon Europe**⁴.

Manuscripts will be accepted in **English, Italian, and Spanish**.

Each author may submit a **maximum of two manuscripts**.

To be eligible, all authors must apply through the **Möbius website** within the application period.

Prize

An overall first prize of **1,500 euro** is awarded for the best story in any of the languages authorized in the contest.

Two prizes of **500 euro each** will be awarded for the second and third place.

The prizes will be delivered *in kind*. Authors will receive the amount as a voucher redeemable at an online or physical store in their respective country of residence.

The prize amounts are before taxes. In case these prizes are considered taxable income by in vigor regulations, the final amount received by winning authors will be after taxes.

Evaluation criteria and communication of results

The evaluation committee, formed by representatives of project partners EURECAT and BOOKABOOK. They will be responsible of selecting the winning manuscript/s under the following criteria:

- Excellence and originality of the manuscript.
- Alignment to the theme: the future we dream about.

³ EU-27: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden.

⁴ Associated countries: Iceland, Norway. In negotiation (as of 4/10/2021): Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Israel, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, Morocco, North Macedonia, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_horizon-euratom_en.pdf

- Its potential for creating a compelling multimedia experience (e.g., through rich sceneries, soundscapes, dialogues, etc.)

The jury might decide not to award any of the prizes if none of the manuscripts are considered suitable for the purposes of the project.

The verdict of the Evaluation Committee will be unappealable.

Winning authors will be notified before **March 15, 2022**

Results will be published on the website before **April 15, 2022**

IP rights

The winning manuscripts will be used to create the Möbius Book experimental production. The Möbius consortium will produce audiovisual, artistic, and creative works based on the manuscript contents to create a digital, cross-media book experience.

The resulting experimental productions will not be commercialized, by any means or purpose. They will become part of the Möbius project demonstrations, which will be showcased and disseminated in relevant venues and events, as planned by the project.

The experimental productions, in full or partially, will remain publicly available in the project website up until 5 years after the project's end (ca. February 2029). The EC may further disseminate the experimental productions as good practices and highlighted project results.

To achieve this purpose, the winning author(s) will grant a non-exclusive license to EURECAT, as coordinator of project Möbius, allowing the exercise of the non-commercial rights of reproduction, communication to the public, and the right of distribution for the period starting from the day the author is communicated the award until February 2029.

EURECAT will acquire the rights to perform the following necessary acts for the purpose of the project:

- The right to translate the manuscript (in full or partially) to English, and any other language to facilitate participatory activities with users.
- The right of reproduction, the right of publication of digital and/or printed copies of the Work including translated versions, as ebooks, and as audiobooks.

Data protection

BOOKABOOK is the controller for processing the personal data that is required to register for the contest. BOOKABOOK values privacy and is committed to comply with the GDPR for all processing activities.

BOOKABOOK will collect and process the necessary data for the contest including contact information from authors, age, citizenship, place of residence, gender, and the manuscript text. BOOKABOOK will keep the data for the duration of the project until all project reporting is finalised. Only the texts of the manuscripts in contest will be shared in a form with employees

of the companies and organizations we work with in the context of Möbius for the evaluation process.

In the case of being one of the winners in any of the categories of the open call for manuscripts, the author authorizes the publication of their name in the Möbius project website, and on own or external media. The winning authors may opt for not sharing their image in the project website and social media accounts.

The author is informed that they have the right to revoke this consent at any time and to exercise the rights of access, rectification, and deletion of data, by contacting BOOKABOOK Data Protection Officer at: mobius@bookabook.it

Please note that the revocation of consent during the call evaluation process will automatically mean the withdrawal of the work from the contest.

Please note that BOOKABOOK capacity for deleting all data instances *a posteriori* may not be possible after being shared on the website, and other online platforms.

Authors are also informed that they can make a complaint to the control authority at <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/>

5. Web submission form (Typeform)

1 → Hi! We're happy to see your interest in our call for manuscripts! *

In order to proceed with your application we need some information. Please share below your full name.

Type your answer here.

press Enter ↵

^ v

2 → Are you over the age of 18? *

^ v

3 → What's your date of birth? *

Month Day Year

____ / ____ / ____

OK ✓ press **Enter** ↵

4 → What is your nationality? *

P.S. Your work is eligible for this call regardless of your citizenship as long as you are a resident in any EU-27 country, or Horizon Europe Associated Countries, as listed in the Terms & Conditions of the call.

Type or select an option ▼

OK ✓

5 → Where are you from? *

Please, insert your Country of residence here
P.S. Your work is eligible for this call regardless of your place of residence as long as you are a citizen of any EU-27 country, or Horizon Europe Associated Countries, as listed in the Terms & Conditions of the call.

Type or select an option

OK ✓

6 → Which city are you from? *

Please, insert your City of residence here

Type your answer here...

OK ✓

press Enter ↵

7 → To which gender identity do you most identify? *

This question is asked for statistical purposes only

- A Man (including transgender men)
- B Non-Binary
- C Woman (including transgender women)
- D Gender-fluid
- E Prefer not to say
- F Other

OK ✓

8 → Yay! We're almost there, we just need a couple more details *

Please, write your email here

name@example.com

OK ✓

press Enter ↵

10 → Privacy Policy *

Please, read about our privacy policy [here](#)

Authors can contact BOOKABOOK Data Protection Officer at:
mobius@bookabook.it

Do you accept the privacy policy agreement?

A I accept

B I don't accept

^ v

11 → Terms & Conditions *

Your application is conditioned to the acceptance and compliance with the Terms and Conditions of the Möbius call for manuscripts. Please read the [Terms & Conditions](#) carefully before applying. Do you accept the Terms&Conditions?

A I accept

B I don't accept

^ v

Figures 4-13. Screenshots of the Typeform.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME!

we can't wait to read your story

Description (optional)

Figure 14. Screenshot of the Typeform ending A.

SO SORRY!

unfortunately we can't accept your application, but you can still be part of this project and read the manuscripts that we'll publish on our website

Thank you for your time!

Figure 15. Screenshot of the Typeform ending B (for applicants under 18y.o., not accepting the Privacy Policy or the Terms&Conditions).

6. Conclusions

The preparation of the open call was an effort intensive task. Smooth cooperation between all partners lead to the definition of the eligibility criteria, IP rights, prizes, and submission and evaluation workflows compliant with data protection and privacy. The call launch is accompanied by a carefully curated communication and dissemination strategy to maximize subscription until the call closing on January 15th, 2022.

Any further action and the results of the call for manuscripts will be dully reported in the First periodic report.